

FL-CHEMSAFE: Advancing Safety Assessment of Chemicals Through Federated Learning

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Abstract

Federated learning has emerged as a promising approach to drug discovery, with real-world implementations such as MELLODY [1] and Effiris [2]. Yet, its application to chemical safety assessment remains unexplored. Data is often siloed, proprietary, or costly to generate. This presentation will discuss how federated learning approaches can overcome data fragmentation in chemical safety assessment. Three use cases were simulated with the Flower open-source federated learning framework, namely (i) federated analytics for dermal permeability (log K_p) screening; (ii) federated convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for mutagenicity prediction from SMILES strings, and (iii) federated eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) models for predicting skin sensitisation potential using molecular fingerprints and descriptors. The results show that federated learning can achieve predictive performance comparable to centralised models while expanding the applicability domain, raising important considerations around model governance. By facilitating model development across distributed, proprietary datasets without compromising confidentiality, federated learning can enhance Next-Generation Risk Assessment through more comprehensive and accurate chemical safety assessment.

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References:

[1] Heyndrickx W., et. al. *J Chem Inf Model*, 64(7), 2024, 2331-2344.

[2] Bassani D., et. al. *Chem Res Toxicol*, 36(9), 2023, 1503-1517.